

Atlantic Ecosystems Assessment, Forecasting & Sustainability

Deliverable 9.3 - AtlantECO Training Resources

Dissemination level: Public

Related Work Package	WP9 Communication, capacity building and outreach
Related task(s)	Task 9.2 Ocean Literacy and public engagement and Task 9.3. Capacity building and training
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Due date	30.06.2025
Submission date	25.02.2026
Type	Report
Status and version	Final submitted version

Declaration: Any work or result described therein is a genuine output of the AtlantECO project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant.

Table of Content

1 Version History	3
2 Executive summary	4
3 Introduction	5
4 Section title	6
4.1 Subtask 9.3.2 Summer schools and training workshops (lead: EMBRC-UGent)	6
4.2 Subtask 9.3.3 South America - Ocean Sampling Day (SA-OSD) (UFSCar)	13
4.3. Mapping existing training activities relevant to AtlantECO	15
5 Conclusion	23

List of tables of figures and of tables

- Figure 1: First training course participants gender distribution
- Figure 2: First training course participants (origin) geographical distribution
- Figure 3: Second training course participants gender distribution
- Figure 4: Second training course participants (origin) geographical distribution
- Figure 5: Third training course participants gender distribution
- Figure 6: Third training course participants (origin) geographical distribution
- Figure 7 :Ocean Sampling Day(s) participants gender distribution
- Figure 8: Ocean Sampling Day(s) participants (origin) geographical distribution
- Figure 9: Number of hits for each of the keywords selected for the 2 different periods
- Figure 10: Number of times the selected keywords are used by each of the top-20 Training Providers
- Figure 11: Number of training events (all levels) per provider for the 2 periods (only top 20 providers shown)
- Figure 12: Language used for training versus type of training
- Figure 13: Evolution of Training types available
- Figure 14: Evolution of Training Languages (2015–2019 vs 2020–2025)
- Figure 15: (Country) Course venues (2015–2019)
- Figure 16: (Country) Course venues (2020–2025)

1 Version History

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
0.1	C. Delgado	Final draft	16.02.2025
1.0	S. Pesant	Review	20.02.2025
1.1	C. Delgado	Added training mapping and gaps Added contributor	24.02.2026

2 Executive summary

This deliverable describes the training activities implemented during the AtlantECO Project, including (subtask 9.3.2) three advanced training courses and (subtask 9.3.3) training activities organised under the Ocean Sampling Day(s). The content and access to training resources used during the events is provided. Furthermore, we provide the geographical distribution and gender balance of the trainees.

3 Introduction

WP9 Communication, capacity building and outreach (M01-48) Leads FTO/UNESCO

The objectives of this WP were as follows:

1. Promoting the project as a whole, including efforts on communication on the Belem Declaration vision and principles of the All Atlantic scientific cooperation flagship.
2. Promoting Ocean Literacy (in particular for the Atlantic) to achieve Ocean Citizen Engagement and raise awareness on ocean health and sustainability.
3. Structuring and sharing the multidisciplinary knowledge of AtlantECO through an integrated Capacity *building* program on next generation observation methods and predictive models.

This deliverable report focuses specifically on the last overarching objective, as a means to transfer capacity and knowledge on next generation observation methods and predictive models for the Atlantic Basin. This report describes the training activities implemented and compiles key information and data on the training activities, as well as pointing to the repositories where the training material is stored/available for further use and dissemination.

4 Section title

4.1 Subtask 9.3.2 Summer schools and training workshops (lead: EMBRC-UGent)

The AtlantECO Training courses were organised by EMBRC/UGent (Marine Training Unit), in close collaboration with AtlantECO PIs. The training courses targeted AtlantECO Consortium young researchers (ECOPs/ECRs), including the ones participating on the All Atlantic Ocean Sampling Day. Training modules were made available online (EMBRC Marine Training Portal). Three Thematic courses were delivered (years 2022, 2024 and 2025). EMBRC/UGent - Marine Training Unit were In charge of organising the course outreach and dissemination, registration and logistics as well as coordinating the course design with the training content providers and uploading training resources on the e-Learning Platform (eLP). The training course details can be traced back on the Marine Training Portal and the resources used during the training sessions remain available on the eLP, Including beyond the conclusion of the AtlantECO Project. Certificates of Attendance were issued digitally through the eLP and can be validated anywhere in the world through an unique code.

4.1.1 First Training Course (2022)

The first training course '**AtlantECO South Africa Training school: AtlantECO Hands-on Training Course Sampling and analysis methods for marine microbiomes, plastics and the plastisphere**' took place in Cape Town and Pretoria (South Africa) between 25 April and 7 May 2022.

All the details about the training event can be found on the Marine Training Course Catalogue: <https://www.marinetraining.eu/node/6078/>.

All the training resources made available by the training content providers is available on EMBRC/Marine Training eLearning Platform: <https://oceantraining.eu/moodle/course/view.php?id=120>.

Course description

This training course aimed at training early stage researchers (ESR) on AtlantECO's standard sampling and sample analysis methods for the study of marine microbiomes, microplastics and the plastisphere, specifically:

- Providing an overview and generate interest in sampling & analysis protocols
- Foster a network of individuals/labs along the Atlantic coast of Africa
- Set the stage for coordinated sampling efforts, including the All Atlantic Ocean Sampling Day (September 21st - equinox)

Course Contents

Introduction. Training Course programme, ESRs flash presentations, AtlantECO
Module 1. Sampling microbiomes, microplastics and the plastisphere at sea
Module 2. Sampling microbiomes, microplastics and the plastisphere in rivers
Module 3. Image analysis of microbiomes, microplastics and plastisphere samples
Module 4. Genetic analysis of microbiomes and plastisphere samples (part 1)
Module 5. Genetic analysis of microbiomes and plastisphere samples (part 2)
Module 6. Biobanking samples, curating & safeguarding data, and sharing data & benefits

Learning outcomes

Key topics: sampling, microbiomes, microplastics, plastisphere, sea, rivers, image analysis, genetic analysis, biobanking, data management. Access and Benefit Sharing

Format: onsite

Main Instructors and Contributors:

- Stéphane Pesant (EMBL-EBI)
- Thomas Leeuw (UMaine)
- Paula Huber (UFSCar)
- Jean-François Chiglione (CNRS)
- Valérie Barbe (CEA)
- Linda Amaral Zettler (NIOZ)
- Raffaella Casotti (SZN)
- Jessica Song (NIOZ-SZN)
- Peter Ryan (UCT)
- Kyle MacLean (UCT)
- Gleice Souza (USP)
- Amanda Elineau (IMEV)
- Klaas Deneudt (VLIZ)
- Clara Trello (Roscoff)
- Noan Le Bescot (TernogLab)
- Anna Oddone (PlanktonPlanet)
- Thulani Makhalanyane (UP)
- Oliver Mogase-Bezuidt (UP)
- Rian Pierneef (ARC)
- María Huete-Ortega (EMBRC-SP)
- Melanthia Stravroulaki (EMBRC-GR)
- Juliette Schramm (Fondation Tara Ocean)

Participation

The training course was attended by 14 Trainees and supported by 22 Trainers. Gender balance and geographical distribution can be seen on the following graphics.

Figure 1: First training course participants gender distribution.

Figure 2: First training course participants (origin) geographical distribution.

4.1.2 Second Training Course (2024)

The second training course '**Complexity and emergence in marine ecosystems: theory, processes and data**' took place in Ischia (Italy) between 24 - 28 June 2024. This training event was organised jointly with [Mission Atlantic](#) and [BIOcean5D](#).

All the details about the training event can be found on the Marine Training Course Catalogue: <https://www.marinetraining.org/node/5881>

All the training resources made available by the training content providers is available on the EMBC Marine Training eLearning Platform: <https://oceantraining.eu/moodle/course/view.php?id=156>

Course description

This course aims at creating a new cohort of researchers who will be able to refine and address the most important theoretical and experimental challenges in the context of open ocean seascape ecology. That is, to introduce the ocean fluid dynamics into current theoretical frameworks (community structure, biogeographies, niche concept, effectiveness of the active tracer response, persistence and fitness, possible functional redundancy, stability of the metabolic machinery with respect to species turnover, etc.) and in the design of new multidisciplinary studies.

Course contents

- Complex System Theories and theoretical ecology
- Biophysical coupling / Ocean Physics / Climate dynamics
- Advanced Data analysis (combining heterogeneous data)/ Niche modelling / Bioinformatic / etc

Learning outcomes

Key topics: community structures and functioning, reactive dynamics, emerging patterns and predictability for pelagic oceanic ecosystems, i.e., ecosystems whose substrate is a fluid.

Format: onsite

Instructors

- Meike Vogt (ETHZ, Switzerland)
- Lucie Bittner (Sorbonne Université, France)
- Damien Eveillard (Université de Nantes, France)
- Enrico Ser Giacomo (CSIC-UIB, Spain)
- Samir Suweis (University of Padua, Italy)
- Alejandro Maass (UCHile, Chile)
- Daniele De Angelis (URoma, Italy)
- Lucia Campese (SZN, Italy)
- Makoto Saito (WHOI, USA)
- Bruno Buongiorno Nardelli (CNR, Italy)
- Daniele Iudiconi (SZN, Italy)

Participation

The training course was attended by 17 Trainees and supported by 12 Trainers. Gender balance and geographical distribution can be seen on the following graphics.

Figure 3: Second training course participants gender distribution.

Figure 4: Second training course participants (origin) geographical distribution.

4.1.3 Third Training Course (2025)

The third training course '**AtlantECO: One Ocean, One Health: Multi-Omics Hackathon**' took place in Ponta Delgada (Azores, Portugal) between 8 - 12 September 2025, back-to-back with the **AtlantECO Final Scientific Conference: One Ocean, One Health Microbiomes of the Atlantic Seascape** (15 - 19 September 2025). This training event was organised in a blended format, i.e., participants attending the onsite phase followed a (mandatory) remotely in advance a series of online training modules designed to better prepare them to take full advantage of the onsite, hands-on training supervised by the training providers.

All the details about the training event can be found on the Marine Training Course Catalogue: <https://www.marinetraining.eu/node/6150>.

All the training resources made available by the training content providers is available on EMBRC/Marine Training eLearning Platform: <https://oceantraining.eu/moodle/course/view.php?id=175>

Course description

The Hackathon addressed simple, but challenging questions using a combination, or a comparison of environmental genomics, proteomics, metabolomics and phenomics (imaging) data from [Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO](#).

The Hackathon consisted of a series of online, self-paced learning modules about

1. the nature, potential and limitation of omics data;
2. accessing omics data programmatically; and
3. novel analysis approaches to combine and/or compare multi-omics data.

During the onsite phase, participants met in person for 5 days (8-12 September) to work in small teams and hack the data and rise to the challenge. Participants were encouraged to join the [AtlantECO Final Scientific Conference](#) the following week in the Azores (15-19 September 2025) in order to present the Hackathon results.

The Hackathon was a good complement to the 2nd [AtlantECO's Synergy Summer School](#) on Complexity and emergence in marine ecosystems/seascape: theory, mechanisms and data, that took place in Italy (June 30 - July 4 2025).

Course contents

Online (self-paced) phase (July/August 2025)

- Module 1. The nature of 'omics data
 - Background reading/recorded material x4 'omics data types
 - Recorded presentation (min 15 min) x4 'omics data types
 - Quiz
- Module 2. The power and limitations of 'omics data
 - Background reading/recorded material x4 'omics data types
 - Recorded presentation (min 15 min) x4 'omics data types
 - Quiz
- Module 3. Accessing 'omics data
 - Background reading/recorded material x4 'omics data types + environmental data + metadata
 - Recorded presentation (min 15 min) x4 'omics data types + environmental data + metadata
 - Quiz
- Module 4. Complex systems approaches and network analysis
 - Background reading/recorded material x3
 - Recorded presentation (min 15 min) x3
 - Quiz

Onsite Hackathon (8-12 September 2025)

General programme of the in-person hackathon:

1. Monday (pm): Flash presentations by participants & discussion on the hackathon "challenges"
2. Tuesday (am)(pm): Teamwork, mentoring clinics & end-of-day debrief of progress
3. Wednesday (am)(pm): Teamwork, mentoring clinics & end-of-day debrief of progress
4. Thursday (am)(pm): Teamwork (work on presentation/pitch), presentation clinic & end-of-day presentation of pitches
5. Friday (am)(pm): Teamwork (finalising analyses & presentation/pitch)

Learning outcomes

By the end of the training course, the learner should be able to:

- describe the nature of each 'omics data type
- explain the power (potential use) of each 'omics data type
- access each 'omics data type
- combine and analyse the different types of 'omics data
- critically address questions/challenges with multi-omics data

Format: blended

Instructors

Academic Mentors

- Genomics: [Dr. Lois Maignien](#), Université de Bretagne Occidentale (UBO), France
- Proteomics: [Dr. Mak Saito](#), Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI), USA
- Metabolomics: [Dr. Georg Pohnert](#), Friedrich Schiller University Jena (FSU), Germany

- Complex systems approach: [Dr. Ferenc Jordan](#), Keynote Research Korlatolt Felelossegu Tarsasag (KNR), Hungary
- Network analysis: [Dr. Samuel Chaffron](#), Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS), France

Data infrastructure Mentors

- Provenance metadata: [Dr. Stéphane Pesant](#), European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), UK
- Genomics: [ENA](#) / [MGnify](#) Ekaterina Sakharova, European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), UK

Participation

The training course was attended by 16 Trainees and supported by 7 Trainers. Gender balance and geographical distribution can be seen on the following graphics.

Figure 5: Third training course participants gender distribution.

Figure 6: Third training course participants (origin) geographical distribution.

4.2 Subtask 9.3.3 South America - Ocean Sampling Day (SA-OSD) (UFSCar)

The [South America Ocean Sampling Day \(SA-OSD\)](#) is a continental coordinated sampling initiative focused on the study of coastal marine microbiomes through the application of harmonised molecular protocols. The initiative was launched to strengthen South American participation in large-scale ocean microbiome research and to generate comparable datasets from South America, a region historically underrepresented in global ocean observing efforts. This initiative arises within the framework of the AtlantECO (EU-H2020) project and is based on synergies with the global Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) initiative.

Since its inception in 2022, the SA-OSD has implemented annual coordinated sampling campaigns, engaging more than 30 research institutions across South America. To date (January 2026), the network has involved a total of 64 participants from 6 Latin America countries.

The initiative brings together a growing network of laboratories that collaboratively conduct simultaneous coastal sampling, apply standardised molecular and metadata protocols, and promote open science practices, while integrating capacity development, training, and outreach activities at local and regional scales.

Figure 7 :Ocean Sampling Day(s) participants gender distribution.

Figure 8: Ocean Sampling Day(s) participants (origin) geographical distribution.

The SA-OSD combines hands-on training, early career researcher engagement, and outreach actions that strengthen ocean literacy and support open science practices across South Atlantic coastal regions, in alignment with the All-Atlantic vision promoted by AtlantECO. SA-OSD was organised as a coordinated annual coastal sampling event, supported by continuous capacity-building actions implemented locally by participating research groups. These activities specifically targeted early career researchers (PhD students and postdoctoral researchers), undergraduate students nearing completion of their degrees, and school communities, thereby linking research, education, and societal outreach.

Capacity development and training activities

During the annual SA-OSD sampling day, several participating research institutions organised on-site training activities in which undergraduate students from marine science, biology, environmental sciences, and related degree programmes were invited to actively participate. These activities were conducted in Spanish or Portuguese, depending on the country of origin of the participating institution, thereby ensuring accessibility and effective engagement of local students. These activities included:

- Demonstrations of field sampling procedures for coastal marine microbiome studies;
- Hands-on exposure to laboratory workflows, including sample filtration, preservation, and preparation for molecular analyses;
- Introduction to molecular protocols used for the study of marine microbial diversity and functions, with an emphasis on standardised and harmonised methodologies.

These activities provided students with early exposure to next-generation observation methods and reinforced links between academic training and large-scale international research initiatives.

Outreach and ocean literacy actions

In addition to sampling-oriented training activities, SA-OSD implemented outreach actions specifically designed to promote ocean literacy and citizen engagement. [Educational flyers](#) and [communication materials](#) (in English, Spanish and Portuguese) were developed and distributed by participating groups to support activities with schools and local communities. These materials introduced key concepts related to ocean health, microbial life in marine ecosystems, and the role of scientific observation in understanding and protecting the ocean.

Several research teams complemented the distribution of these materials with school-oriented activities, linking the sampling event to broader discussions on marine ecosystems, sustainability, and the importance of science for environmental stewardship.

4.3. Mapping existing training activities relevant to AtlantECO

In order to map the training opportunities related to the AtlantECO topics, we used the EMBRC-ERIC Marine Training Portal (www.marinetraining.eu) database (data extracted 3 February 2026).

Disclaimer: even though the Marine Training Portal is the largest global database of marine and maritime related training opportunities, including over a 1000 (training) providers from over 80 countries, we cannot guarantee the database is absolutely complete. The data and information extracted should therefore be used taking this possible limitation into account.

To collect the data, we searched for training opportunities that include the following keywords and across 2 periods: 1) 2015 - 2019 (prior to AtlantECO project and 2) 2020 - 2025 (during the AtlantECO project):

- Plankton
- Microbiome
- Genomics
- Metabolomics
- Proteomics
- Image/Imaging
- Bioinformatics

A total of 313 training opportunities mentioned at least one of the keywords above: n=111 (2015 - 2019) and n=202 (2020 - 2025).

Figure 9: Number of hits for each of the keywords selected for the 2 different periods.

Training Providers

The training providers are based mainly in Europe and the United States of America. Providers like the Technical University of Denmark, Nord University, University of Copenhagen, University of Delaware, and University of Plymouth have significant activity in 2020–2025, with little or none in 2015–2019. On the other hand, some providers (e.g., Istituto di Scienze Marine, Universiteit Gent) appear mainly or exclusively in 2015–2019, representing earlier training efforts.

Figure 10: Number of times the selected keywords are used by each of the top-20 Training Providers.

Figure 11: Number of training events (all levels) per provider for the 2 periods (only top 20 providers shown).

Language of Training Provision and Types of Training

The English language is widely used for training provision, regardless of the type of training. This may reflect the strong international orientation of training activities. Short type, informal training courses and workshops dominate both periods, but formal academic programmes expand sharply in 2020–2025. This may indicate an increasing momentum of the AtlantECO topics in full academic programmes compared to the earlier years.

Figure 12: Language used for training versus type of training.

Evolution of Training Types (2015-2019 vs 2020-2025)

Figure 13: Evolution of Training types available.

Figure 14: Evolution of Training Languages (2015–2019 vs 2020–2025)

Venue Country Distribution

Most training available in the selected topics is available in the Northern/Western Hemisphere. However, during the second period, it was possible to see an expansion, namely towards Northern European countries as well as the USA.

Figure 15: (Country) Course venues (2015–2019).

Figure 16: (Country) Course venues (2020–2025)

5 Conclusion

Training activities during the AtlantECO Project were implemented under 2 main pillars: 1) advanced training courses and 2) informal, 1-day training sessions designed around the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD). Whilst the former were structured training courses targeting Early Career Researchers and often included further self-paced learning and preparation to be done remotely, the latter were designed as informal, citizen science and citizen engagement activities. Given this character, the OSD activities were adapted and translated to the local languages. The contents shared during the advanced training courses remain available on EMBRC's Marine Training eLearning Platform.

Overall, these activities trained no less than 110 people from both sides of the Atlantic Ocean and mobilized over 40 trainers from the consortium. It is worth noting that the gender participation is clearly biased towards more women attending the training opportunities.

Altogether, the training activities implemented worked as a platform for early career researchers not only from the AtlantECO Consortium but also outside it, thus fostering peer-to-peer exchanges, sharing of protocols and training materials, and collective learning around sampling standardisation, data generation, and open science practices. Through a combination of onsite and remote learning opportunities as well as coordinated sampling actions, these project activities fostered early career researcher engagement, as well as school-children oriented outreach actions, and as such contributed to the structuring and dissemination of multidisciplinary knowledge, reinforcing capacity exchange and knowledge transfer as well as ocean literacy activities.

The training mapping exercise showed that there are still a limited number of training opportunities in these specific topics. However, there was a strong growth in the number of trainings in 2020–2025. Whilst in the first period training was available in a very small number of countries (mainly Western/Southern European countries), the period 2020–2025 showed a marked expansion in the United States, Denmark and Norway, as well as in France and the United Kingdom.

Considering the type of training, the first period was dominated by short training courses and workshops only, whilst the second period saw a sharp rise in formal degree programmes (the topics being embedded in academic level training (BSc, MSc, PhD) with higher weight in the more advanced level degrees.

The top training providers include the Technical University of Denmark, Nord University, University of Copenhagen, University of Delaware and University of Plymouth. These are largely active in 2020–2025 rather than 2015–2019.

The training mapping exercise showed a few clear gaps: 1) the geographic coverage is highly uneven, with overwhelming concentration in Europe and the USA, moderate growth in Asia, and major gaps in the Global South. 2) Language: English dominates the training offer, with only a few courses being held in other languages, which may limit accessibility for regions where English proficiency is low. Additionally, given that the most recent training is mainly available as part of formal education, there is a shortage of training opportunities for established professionals (lifelong-learning opportunities). Also, the scarcity of remote/online training opportunities limits the possibility for upskilling in the professional context.